

Form and Forming of the Eco-Lexicons of Balinese PAON

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Abstract

Balinese language is the mother tongue of Balinese ethnic. Balinese language a rich language, therefore it becomes the object of many linguists. This research aims at finding out the Balinese lexicons found in *Paon* 'Balinese traditional kitchen and analyzing the forming forms of the lexicons as found in Balinese traditional kitchen. This is an interdisciplinary research which combine the study of language and ecology. The data were collected by applying observation method through interview and note taking techniques. The analysis was done through applying qualitative method using the theory of Eco linguistics and morphology. The research shows that the lexicon used in *paon* are classified into noun, verb and adjective. The forming forms of those lexicons can be categorized into based form, through affixation, compounding and reduplication form.

1. Introduction

Eco-linguistics is a branch of linguistics which deals with the study of language and environment. Language as a communication tool is tightly related to the living environment, therefore language can be a living document of human's history. Haugen (1972) has defined that language ecology is a study of interaction between language and environment. Verbal forms which contain the meaning of environment exist in certain language cover the speakers' knowledge of the ecology where they live.

Bali is one of the provinces in Indonesia which is really famous for its culture. The culture of Balinese is tightly bound with Hinduism. The community of Balinese who are Hindus dominate the inhabitant of Bali Island as mention by Central Bureau of Statistics (*Badan Pusat Statistik*) Balinese Province, 86, 59% are Hindus form the total number of 4.344.554 people who live in Bali. Besides the

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influence of Hindu religion, the culture of Balinese is built by one of the main components which is Balinese language.

Balinese ethnic use Bali language as their mother tongue. The use of Indonesian language is mainly in formal domain. The position of Balinese language is not only as a communication tool but it is one of the identities of Balinese people. Balinese language use in a very high domain like in religious activities. As what already stated by Suastra (2009) Balinese language is the symbol of Balinese ethnic. Knowing this importance, Balinese language should be maintained and use by generation to generation in order Balinese culture is preserved and survived.

Tourism industry and globalization have given significant impact to the way living of Balinese people. Modernisation has resulted the ecological changes in the community. In terms of the language use, there are many new lexicons appear and take the position of Balinese lexicon in its use, it can be concluded that the impact of ecological changes also changes the language. One of the significant changes in Balinese life is how modernization influence their domestic activities like how modern invention has resulted the change of balinese kitchen from traditional. The number of traditional kitchens '*paon*' getting decrease.

Traditional kitchen, in Balinese which is named *paon* is not only a place or domestic are of cooking but it has many functions. The basic function which is practical is a place of cooking, in which there are many kitchen's equipments and activities exist in this area. Another function is related to Balinese belief that *paon* is a place of neutralizing bad spirit or purifying bad things form outside area of the house, therefore Balinese will enter the *paon* before entering the other parts of the house. Why this becomes one of the beliefs and becomes the habit, it is because in Hindu Bali, *paon* is the place of God Brahma and Agni who possess the power to burn any existing bad spirit. Wiastina Putra dan Yulianasari (2020) explained that, the God of Agni exists in the traditional stove '*jalikan*' who has the power of burning as fire, meanwhile the God of Brahma exist in the special place named as *pelangkiran*.

Modern kitchen which exists because of modern needs of course has many differences compared to *paon*. Modern kitchen is fully equipped by modern tools but *paon* use traditional equipments. Different naming of the kitchen's equipment has impacted different naming of activities occurred. Young generation of Balinese might be not familiar with the naming of traditional in Balinese since the nouns are hardly found because they already replaced by modern equipment. Besides the nouns, the number of Balinese verbs related to *paon* are stranges for them.

The lexicon of Balinese language related to *paon* are many, this is one of the richness of Balinese language. The story of Balinese way of living is documented in this area. *Paon* is the main building in Balinese house, it has special position and function. Besides that *paon* is rich of lexicons, therefore this study is interested in finding out the form and forming process of the eco lexicon of Balinese *paon*.

2. Materials and Methods

Ecolinguistics

Ecolinguistics is an interdisciplinary study between linguistics and ecology. The idea of ecolinguistic studies was mentioned by Gumperz (1962). It is initiated by Gumperz (1962) who stated that sociolinguistics is the study of verbal behavior which is related to the social characteristics of speakers, their cultural background, and the ecological nature of the environment in which they interact (Gumperz, 1962: 137). Moreover Haugen (1972) proposed a definition of language ecology, namely the study of interactions between language and the environment. This can be interpreted that

Eco linguistics is the study of interactions between language and its environment. Fill (1993:126) in Lindo and Simonsen (2000: 40) states that ecolinguistics is an umbrella for all research on language that is linked to ecology. Language can represent facts about natural, social and cultural life that exist in the environment (Fill and Muhlhausler, 2001)

Form and Forming eco lexicons

Booij (2007) argues that 'the lexicon specifies the properties of each word, its phonological form, its morphological, and syntactic properties, and its meaning' (Booij, 2007:16). It can be understood that the lexicon is considered to be able to determine the nature of each word, its phonological form, morphological form, and syntactic properties as well as the meaning of the lexicon. The study of form and forming ecollexicon concern in word formation which is part of morphology. Morphology is a part of micro linguistics that discusses or studies the ins and outs of word structure and the influence of changes in word structure on word classes and word meanings. Booij (2007) states that knowledge of a language involves knowledge of the system of relationships between word forms and word meanings. Morphology is the study of the internal constituent structure of words (Booij, 2007: 4).

This research uses a qualitative approach. The type of data in this paper is qualitative data because it is in the form of words or sentences. Qualitative data consists of words related to paon. List of lexicons obtained from sources and also through observations of paon. One of the characteristics of qualitative research is that the researcher acts as both an instrument and a data collector. This research uses the observation method with interview techniques. The observation method is to observe language related to the kitchen lexicons of Balinese society. This interview was conducted with sources who knew in depth about the existence of the paon along with the building structures, tools and activities carried out in the paon. The data analysis method uses a qualitative descriptive method. The form of data analyzed at lexicon level is analyzed using qualitative analysis by describing it in clear, effective and well-structured language.

3. Results and Discussions

Bali is a province that is unique. With the condition of society where the majority adheres to Hinduism, Balinese people have very high religious values. All aspects of Balinese life are regulated by the religious philosophical concepts of Hinduism. One aspect of Hindu religious life is that Hindu society manages its life based on three basic concepts to maintain a harmonious relationship with the elements of life that are believed to exist in this world. These three basic concepts are known as *Tri Hita Karana*, which consists of *Parahyangan* (maintaining a harmonious relationship with the divine), *Pawongan* (maintaining a harmonious relationship with fellow humans), *Palemahan* (maintaining a harmonious relationship with nature). This concept is also implemented in the order of determining the location of Balinese paon buildings. Apart from the concept of determining the location of a building, in paon there are also lexicons that embody the knowledge of the Balinese Hindu community in viewing life.

Table 1 Eco-lexicon in the form of Base Words

Eco-lexicon	Forms	Meaning	Reference	
			Biotic	Abiotic
<i>aru</i>	noun	half cooked rice mixed with hot water	√	-

<i>alutan</i>	noun	half burning wood	-	√
<i>andus</i>	noun	smoke	-	√
<i>aon</i>	noun	kitchen ash from burning wood	-	√
<i>daar</i>	verb	to eat	-	-
<i>dadah</i>	verb	to cook, heat in a skillet	-	-
<i>dadang</i>	verb	to heat it and put it near the fire	-	-
<i>dilap</i>	verb	licked by fire	-	-
<i>enjit</i>	verb	burn		
<i>gobed</i>	noun	to grate	-	-
<i>mēm</i>	verb	to soak	-	√
<i>beruk</i>	noun	water container from coconut shells	√	-
<i>buki/boki</i>	noun	an old clay pot	-	√
<i>bungbung</i>	noun	water container from bamboo	√	-
<i>canting</i>	noun	small ladle made of coconut shell with stem	√	-
<i>caratan</i>	noun	kettle jug made of clay	-	√
<i>catu</i>	noun	tool measure rice from big coconut shell containing two <i>ce'e'ng</i>	√	-
<i>cééng</i>	noun	tool measure rice from small coconut shell which contains $1/2$ <i>catu</i>	√	-
<i>cobék</i>	noun	bucket made of clay	-	√
<i>dangdang</i>	verb	pot to cook rice	-	√
<i>dungki</i>	verb	small basket for storing fish	√	-
<i>entip</i>	noun	rice crust that sticks to the bottom of the pot/pan	√	-
<i>gebuh</i>	adjective	over boiled		
<i>jukut</i>	noun	vegetable	√	-
<i>jaan</i>	adjective	delicious		
<i>kekeb</i>	noun	steamer cover made of clay	-	√
<i>ngiu/niu</i>	noun	a tool made from circular woven bamboo to separate rice from dirt	√	-
<i>nyangluh</i>	adjective	tasty		√
<i>nyem</i>	adjective	cold, bland		√
<i>payuk</i>	noun	cooking pot		√
<i>paon</i>	noun	Balinese kitchen		√
<i>punapi</i>	noun	place to drying things above the fire furnace	√	
<i>prakpak</i>	noun	torch from dry coconut leaves	√	

<i>saang</i>	noun	firewood	√	-
<i>sémprong</i>	noun	fire extinguisher made of bamboo	√	
<i>sepit</i>	noun	tongs made of bamboo	√	
<i>wareg</i>	adjective	full stomach		√

Table 1 shows the lexicon of *paon* in the form of base words. There are three categories of the lexicon, namely; nouns, verbs, and adjectives. The lexicon in the form of noun can be referred to the ecological side, both biotic and abiotic, such as; *jukut* 'vegetable', *saang* 'firewood, and *sepit* 'tong made of bamboo which are biotic. *Dandang* 'pot to cook rice' and *kekeb* 'steamer cover made of clay' represent abiotic reference. Lexicon in the category of verb and adjective are also found but the number of those lexicon are not many.

Table 2 Eco-lexicon in the Form of Affixation

Eco-lexicon	Affix	Affixation Type	Forms	Meaning	Reference	
					Biotic	Abiotic
<i>mejek</i>	<i>ma-</i>	inflection	verb	to squeeze, crush	-	√
<i>meseng</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to separate water from boiled vegetable	-	√
<i>nadang</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to cook or to dry things by placing it near fire	-	√
<i>nepeng</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to cook rice in a pan	-	√
<i>ngangkid</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to lift the cooked food	-	√
<i>ngaru</i>	<i>ng-</i>	derivation	verb	to mix half-cooked rice with hot water	-	√
<i>nglablab</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to boil	-	√
<i>ngemem</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to soak	-	√
<i>nimbang</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to cook in a raw bamboo tube	-	√
<i>nunu</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to cook above coals	-	√
<i>kikihan</i>	<i>-an</i>	derivation	noun	Grater	-	√
<i>pangésan</i>	<i>pa- -an</i>	derivation	noun	a tool to separate coconut fiber	-	√
<i>penyeluhan</i>	<i>pa- -an</i>	derivation	noun	a tool to separate coconut from its shell	-	√
<i>yaip</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to drain	-	√
<i>nyakan</i>	<i>ng-</i>	inflection	verb	to cook rice	-	√

Affixation Process

Lexicons *paon* use in larger units such as phrases and clauses, especially verbs and nouns will undergo a morphological process. The inflectional and derivational affixes are utilized in forming grammatical words. Prefix *ng-* and *ma-* are applied in forming verbs. Suffix *-an* and circumfix *pa-*, *-an* is applied to form noun from verb. The data below show the affixation process.

1. *ma-* + *bejek* (verb) → *mejek* (verb)
AFFIX squeeze squeezing
2. *ng-* + *jakan* (verb) → *nyakan* (verb)
AFFIX cook cooking
3. *ng-* + *tunu* (verb) → *nunu* (verb)
AFFIX grill grilling

Data 1, 2 and 3 show the affixation process forming active verbs. there are two prefixes use, *ma-* and *ng-*. The underline form prefix *ng-* has the allmorphs {ny, n}. the sound assimilation happens in the process. Prefix *ng-* and *ma-* are categorised into inflectional affixes because they don't change the word category and meaning from the base word.

4. *Ng-* + *aru* (noun) → *ngaru* (verb)
AFFIX half-cooked rice to make aru
5. *Kikih* (verb) + *-an* → *kikihan* (noun)
to grate AFFIX grater
6. *Pa-* + *seluh* (verb) + *-an* → *panyeluhan* (noun)
To separate coconut from the shell tool to separate the coconut

Data 4 until 6 show the application of derivational affixes in forming words in Balinese language. It can be seen that prefix *ng-* in data 4 is different with prefix *ng-* in data 2 and 3. In data 4 prefix *ng-* is functioned to form verb 'ngaru' from the base form noun 'aru'. Data 5 shows the use of suffix *-an* to fom noun 'kikihan' from the base word verb 'kikih'. The use of circumfix *pa-*, *-an* is shown in data 6. This is a kind of circumfix because *pa-* and *-an* are attached simultaneously altogether to the base 'seluh' to become 'panyeluhan'. Prefix *ng-*, suffix *-an*, and circumfix *pa-*, *-an* belong to derivation because the attachment of those affix has resulted the changing of word classes and meaning.

Table 3 Eco-lexicon in the Form of Compound Words

Eco-lexicon	Forms	Meaning	Reference	
			Biotic	Abiotic
<i>gidat jalikan</i>	noun	furnace forehead	-	√

<i>janggar ulam</i>	noun	bay leaf	√	-
<i>ketumbah bolong</i>	noun	kinds of coriander	√	-
<i>nasi dingin</i>	noun	the rest of yesterday's rice	√	-
<i>nasi kepel</i>	noun	rice ball	√	-
<i>basa genep</i>	noun	kind of complete seasoning	√	-
<i>nyem lalah</i>	adjective	specific taste between spicy and less salt	-	√

Compound words are also found, but the number are rare. The combination of two roots has resulted new form with new meaning. For example the word '*gidat jalikan*' is composed by two roots; *gidat* 'forehead' and *jalikan* 'furnace'. This combination produce new word '*gidat jalikan*' which means 'the top front part of furnace'. Compounding also occurs in adjective form '*nyem lalah*' this combination produces new meaning 'specific taste between spicity and less salt'.

Table 4 Eco-lexicon in the Form of Reduplication

Eco-lexicon	Form	Meaning	Reference	
			Biotic	Abiotic
<i>basa-basa</i>	noun	Spices	√	-
<i>kété-kété</i>	noun	clay pot	-	√
<i>anget-angetan</i>	noun	Herbs and spices	√	-

Table 4 shows the eco-lexicon of *paon* was produced thorough word formation process, namely reduplication. The word '*basa-basa*' was formed by reduplicating the root '*basa*' which means spices that usually followed by name of the spices like *basa genep*, *basa gede* and other. The word *basa-basa* as the result of reduplication process means many kinds of raw spices. The word '*kete-kete*' is a pseudo-rephrase word. The form '*kété*' doesn't have any meaning, it is only meaningful when it is reduplicated. The meaning of *kété-kété* is a clay pot used for roasting. The last word '*anget-angetan*' is formed by reduplicating the word '*anget*' an adjective which means 'warm'. In the process of reduplicating suffix *-an* is attached to forms noun because there is no form of *anget-anget* (adj.) in Balinese. The word '*anget-angetan*' means herbs and spices which is usually found in *paon*.

4. Conclusion

The eco-lexicon found in Balinese *paon* can be categorized into noun, verb and adjective. The reference of the eco-lexicons are found both in biotic and abiotic side. Some of the eco-lexicons are formed by following word formation process, such as; affixation, compounding, and reduplication. Kind of affix to form noun, such as; suffix *-an* and confix *pe- -an*. Prefix *ma-* and *ng-* with its allomorph {*ng-*, *ny-*, *n-*} is used to form verb. There are two categorized of affix found in forming the eco-lexicon, namely inflectional affix and derivational affix. Other word formation process found are compounding and reduplication. The Balinese eco-lexicon found in *paon* shows that Balinese language is rich of

lexicon which are related to the ecology of the speakers and the story of human life past through generation.

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